

Guidance and methods for developing and evaluating prompts for large language models in health care: a scoping review protocol

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1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to “a set of advanced technologies that enable machines to do highly complex tasks effectively, which would require intelligence if a person were to perform them ^{1,2}.” AI comprises techniques that enable computers to mimic human behaviour and reproduce, improve or even surpass human decision-making to solve complex tasks independently or with minimal human intervention ^{3,4}. An AI system is a machine-based system that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers from input data how to generate outputs -such as predictions, content or recommendations -that can influence physical or virtual environments. Different AI systems vary in their levels of autonomy, knowledge and adaptiveness after deployment ⁵.

Core technologies powering AI systems include machine learning (ML), which uses historical data to make predictions or decisions, and deep learning, a subset of ML, which uses neural networks to recognise complex patterns. Advances in data availability, computational power, and algorithmic innovation have enabled machines to understand and generate human language, leading to substantial advances in natural language processing. These combined developments have ultimately enabled the emergence of Large Language Models (LLMs)^{6,7}.

1.1 Large Language Models (LLMs) and prompts

LLMs are deep learning systems trained on large datasets to enable them to process user-provided text and generate contextually appropriate responses. The development of LLMs builds on earlier advances in natural language processing, including the emergence of large-scale neural network training efforts such as Google Brain in 2011, and the introduction of models such as BERT in 2018, which improved machines’ ability to understand human language ⁸. With the release of ChatGPT by OpenAI in November 2022, LLMs became widely known to the public and rapidly entered mainstream use ⁹. LLMs have the potential to impact the health field by improving efficiency across a range of tasks, including extracting data from medical records, supporting personalised treatments, helping on tailoring medication instructions, assisting in drug discovery, and interacting with patients, among many other applications¹⁰⁻¹³. In health research, LLMs are also increasingly recognised as valuable tools for tasks such as screening and data extraction in evidence synthesis projects ^{14,15}.

When interacting with LLMs, the input provided to obtain a response is referred to as a *prompt*. A prompt consists of an instruction, a query, or other types of input, such as text or images, that guides a generative LLM to produce a specific output. Prompts play a critical role in shaping the

interaction and the resulting output, as they establish the context, define the desired response, and specify how the content should be presented¹⁶. Therefore, prompts should be deliberately designed, tested, refined, and evaluated, as their wording can strongly influence the model's behaviour. Also, the same input may yield different outputs, and LLMs may occasionally generate incorrect or fabricated information, which must therefore be carefully verified¹⁷.

Since LLMs generate text based on probabilities, several prompt-related factors can influence the quality and reliability of LLM outputs and help reduce incorrect or fabricated responses, often referred to as hallucinations. The quality and reliability of responses depend on prompt design, including the type of prompt (e.g. open-ended instructions or role prompting), its structure, and the extent to which it has been refined¹⁸. In addition, the same prompt may yield different results across LLMs, which can be fine-tuned through instruction-based training or learning with human feedback^{16,19,20}.

1.2 Methods for prompt generation

The generation of a prompt should involve two sequential phases¹⁷:

- 1) **Building phase** (also referred to as prompt development or prompt engineering): A phase during which the prompt is created. An initial prompt is proposed, which is followed by an iterative design process to guide the model toward producing accurate, relevant, and well-structured outputs. Prompts can be created manually by humans or using LLMs. This building phase aims to achieve clarity, correctness, and alignment of the output with a desired format²¹.
- 2) **Validation phase** (also referred to as prompt evaluation): A phase during which the prompt is tested to determine if it performs as intended. Prompts can be evaluated for different aspects, e.g. accuracy, reliability, reproducibility, efficiency, and risks including algorithmic bias¹⁷.

The datasets used to build and validate the prompt must be different. The building phase typically uses a smaller, more representative dataset to capture task variability. The validation phase should use a separate dataset that was not used in prompt development. Ideally, the validation dataset should reflect the type and diversity of data to which the prompt will ultimately be applied, including relevant variations in content and expected outputs. Also, the model output should be reviewed for potential errors. Prompt phases, versions and decisions should be documented to ensure transparency and reproducibility^{17,21}.

LLM developers and engineers have produced guidance on how to generate prompts (19, 22). However, to our knowledge, contextualised guidance for prompt generation in the field of health care is still limited. Examples exist, such as guidelines for radiology (23), integrative medicine (18), or oncology (24). In addition, given the rapid expansion of LLMs and their increasingly diverse applications in health, it is relevant to better understand how prompts applied in this field are developed and evaluated (17).

2 Aim of the scoping review

This scoping review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of prompt generation methods for LLMs, including prompt building and validation, with a focus on health care. The scoping review will have the following specific objectives.

Objective 1. To identify and summarise existing guidance and recommendations for prompt generation for LLMs, including guidance produced by commonly used LLM-based systems and publications with specific guidance for prompt generation in health care.

Objective 2. To describe the methods used in health care studies to generate prompts for LLMs, including approaches for prompt building, validation or both.

3 Methods

This scoping review will follow the JBI methodology^{22,23} and will be based on the JBI template for scoping reviews²⁴. The final publication will be reported according to the Preferred Reporting Items for SRs and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR)²⁵.

3.1 Inclusion criteria

We will use the population, concept and context (PCC) framework for conducting this scoping review²⁶.

3.1.1 Participants (P)

Objective 1: No specific participant criteria apply.

Objective 2: The studies must relate to health care in humans. We will exclude topics without human participants or human data, such as preclinical research in animals or cellular research.

3.1.2 *Concept (C)*

This scoping review will examine the characteristics and approaches used to develop and evaluate prompts for LLMs. We will include studies that include information from any phase of the prompt generation process, such as building or validation.

Objective 1: We will explore the characteristics of guidance for prompt generation. First, we will consider general guidance produced by commonly used LLM-based systems. Second, we will consider guidance specifically addressing prompt generation in health care.

Objective 2: We will explore the methods that have been employed for generating prompts in health care studies.

3.1.3 *Context (C)*

Objective 1: No specific contextual criteria apply.

Objective 2: Only prompts generated within health care will be eligible. Eligible research may address any point along the disease continuum: prevention (including public health, health education and health promotion), diagnosis, treatment, rehabilitation, palliative care) and any health care discipline or setting (in-person or virtual). Prompts developed to accelerate research processes, such as systematic reviews, will also be eligible if the research topic pertains to health care.

3.2 **Types of sources**

We will consider reports published in English after December 1, 2022 (as ChatGPT was launched for public use on November 30, 2022)²⁷. We will exclude reports available only as abstracts (including conference abstracts), social media posts, institutional reports (e.g., theses), and other unpublished documents. Eligible preprints will be tagged as “Studies awaiting classification” and will not be considered included until they are published in a peer-reviewed journal.

The types of sources for objectives 1 and 2 are detailed below.

3.2.1 Objective 1:

- Guidance on prompt generation developed for the commonly used LLM-based systems, such as the following: ChatGPT Claude, Command, Copilot, DeepSeek, Falcon, Grok, Gemini, Llama, Mistral, Stable and Qwen.
- Peer-reviewed published guidance on prompt generation in the health context. Evidence syntheses on this topic will be eligible.

3.2.2 Objective 2:

- Peer-reviewed primary studies that inform how the prompts used in the studies were generated. Studies must have used prompts for LLMs and described the methods used to generate the prompts (development phase, validation phase, both).
- Studies reporting methods for only one phase of the prompt generation (development or validation) will be eligible.
- Studies that used prompts but do not describe the methods used to generate them will be excluded (but tagged and listed in the table of excluded studies).

3.3 Search strategy

An initial search in Medline (Ovid) will be conducted to identify relevant keywords. We will use controlled vocabulary and free terms. An experienced researcher (DBG) will develop the search strategies, and an information specialist (NAD) will conduct a peer review of the search strategies using the PRESS checklist ²⁸ (see Appendix 1).

3.3.1 Searches in electronic databases

We will consult the following electronic databases since 1st December 2022 and limited by English language of publication:

1. MEDLINE (Ovid)
2. EMBASE (Elsevier)
3. CINAHL
4. PsycInfo

3.3.2 Searching other resources

We will conduct a manual search of commonly used LLM-based systems to identify guidance on prompt generation, such as Claude, Command, Copilot, DeepSeek, Falcon, Grok, Gemini, OpenAI, Llama, Mistral, Stable, Qwen. We will consult the reference lists of evidence synthesis publications on the same topic to identify additional studies.

4 Study selection

We will add the search results to EndNote21 and remove duplicates. Following deduplication, we will import citation information into Rayyan³¹. A pilot of the study selection process will be done with a random sample of 500 records (DBG, LFM, CM, AKT, JLA) following a decision flowchart based on the inclusion criteria for the scoping review, which includes illustrative examples (Appendix 2). One reviewer (DBG, LFM, CWA, CM, QG, or AKT) will screen titles and abstracts. A second reviewer (JLA or DBG) will cross-check 10% of the excluded records. We will measure the inter-rater agreement during the title and abstract screening process. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion or by a third reviewer (DBG, JLA, or CW). Two independent reviewers will assess the eligibility of each full text (DBG, LFM, CWA, CM). Disagreements will be resolved by involving a third reviewer (CW, DBG, or JLA).

The results of the searches and the study selection process will be described in the final report and presented in a PRISMA 2020 flow diagram (36).

To assess whether a health study meets the criteria for objective 2—specifically, whether it outlines the methods used to generate the prompts and is therefore eligible—we will also review its appendices and supplementary materials.

Multiple reports relating to the same study (e.g., protocol and final report; successive versions of a living review) will be collated and treated as a single study unit, the most recent or most comprehensive report will be used as the primary reference.

5 Data extraction

Data extraction will be adapted to the review's objectives. We will extract data from the included guidance and research studies using two pre-piloted data extraction forms in Rayyan³¹. We will pilot the data extraction on five guidance documents and 20 studies. One reviewer (AKT, CM, CWA, DBG, LFM or QG) will extract the data and a second one (AKT, DBG, CM, CWA, JLA, LFM or QG) will check the extracted data. Disagreements will be resolved through discussion or by involving a

third author (CW, DBG or JLA). See draft data extraction template in Appendix 3, which will be refined throughout the scoping review process.

We will not contact authors regarding missing or unclear information. We will code unreported or insufficiently described items as “Reported but unclear” or “Not reported” and quantify their frequency, as this may itself provide an insight into reporting practices.

6 Data analysis and presentation

We will analyse and present findings separately for Objective 1 (prompt generation guidance) and Objective 2 (prompt generation methods in health studies), using different code sets in the data extraction form (see Appendix 3).

We will extract the text as reported by the authors. Following data extraction, we will clean and standardise key variables to enable comparison across reports (e.g., LLM names and versions, prompt purposes/tasks, and terminology for the prompt development and validation phases). Where authors use different labels for similar concepts, we will apply a pre-specified coding framework and record the original wording alongside the harmonised code.

We will present a narrative synthesis of the included documents. We will also summarise the study characteristics using proportions or medians and interquartile ranges (IQR) where appropriate. Summary tables will highlight key information, facilitating a clear understanding of the main findings identified in the included studies.

6.1 Objective 1: Guidance documents (LLM developers and health care guidance)

We will map and summarise guidance content to a structured framework that reflects the prompt generation lifecycle (at minimum: building/development and validation/evaluation, plus any additional phases reported, such as deployment, monitoring, or updating).

We will summarise definitions (e.g. prompt and prompt generation), recommended principles/techniques, recommended documentation practices, and suggested evaluation dimensions/metrics.

6.2 Objective 2: Health studies reporting prompt development and/or validation

We will characterise studies descriptively, summarising (as counts/proportions and, where relevant, medians with interquartile ranges): publication year, health field, study design, setting, LLM and version, prompt purpose/task, target population/data, and whether the study reports development, validation, or both.

We will summarise methods for prompt building (e.g., iterative refinement, expert input, use of examples, role prompting, constraints/output schemas, use of test sets during development, among others), and prompt validation (e.g., independent test datasets, benchmarking against reference standards, human evaluation procedures, reproducibility checks, comparisons across LLMs/versions).

We will catalogue performance dimensions and metrics (e.g., accuracy, completeness, inter-rater agreement for human judgements, consistency/reproducibility, efficiency/time, safety or bias-related checks), and group them into a small set of analytically useful categories. We will try to follow the RAISE 2 taxonomy of performance metrics ¹⁷ or other relevant classifications.

We will compare the findings of Objective 1 and Objective 2 using a crosswalk table that shows whether practices recommended in the guidance are used in health studies and where health studies use methods not covered in the guidance.

We will explicitly identify evidence gaps (e.g., absent/rarely reported separation of development vs validation datasets, limited reporting of prompt versions and decision logs, limited evaluation of LLMs biases or safety, limited assessment of generalisability across settings or LLM versions).

7 Acknowledgements

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9 Declarations

Not applicable

10 Author contributions

DBG, JLA and CW conceived this scoping review. DBG and NAD designed and executed preliminary searches. DBG and JLA wrote the first draft of this protocol. All authors read the protocol critically and approved its final version. CW, JLA and JH obtained funding for this scoping review. CW is the guarantor.

11 Conflict of interests

JB offers Academic Writing Courses with custom GPTs created for that purpose.

JM is the co-convenor of the Cochrane Joint Methods AI group.

The remaining authors have no conflicts of interest.

12 Ethics

The project was reviewed by the Ethics Committee of the Canton of Zurich (Switzerland), which concluded that it did not fall under the scope of the Swiss Human Research Act (BASEC-Nr. Req-2024-00971, issued July 2024).

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13 Appendices

13.1 Appendix 1. Search strategy Medline Ovid-1946 to present

Objective 1. Guidance on prompt generation

- 1 Guideline/
- 2 Guid*.ti,ab.
- 3 Strategi*.ti,ab.
- 4 Consensus/
- 5 Consensus.ti,ab.
- 6 or/1-5
- 7 Prompt engineering.ti,ab.
- 8 prompt-engineering techniqu*.ti,ab.
- 9 Prompt* techniques.ti,ab.
- 10 Prompt design.ti,ab.
- 11 Prompt craft*.ti,ab.
- 12 or/7-11
- 13 6 and 12

Objective 2. Methods used for prompt generation in health studies

1 Generative Artificial Intelligence/
2 generative artificial intelligence.ti,ab.
3 Large Language Models/
4 large language model*.ti,ab.
5 LLM.ti,ab.
6 LLMs.ti,ab.
7 GenAI.ti,ab.
8 natural language processing/
9 natural language processing.ti,ab.
10 NLP.ti,ab.
11 Chatbot.ti,ab.
12 Artificial Intelligence/
13 Artificial Intelligence.ti,ab.
14 AI.ti,ab.
15 Claude.ti,ab.
16 Copilot.ti,ab.
17 DeepSeek.ti,ab.
18 Falcon.ti,ab.
19 Grok.ti,ab.
20 Gemini.ti,ab.
21 GPT.ti,ab.
22 OpenAI.ti,ab.
23 Llama.ti,ab.
24 Mistral.ti,ab.
25 Qwen.ti,ab.
26 Stable LM.ti,ab.
27 Command A.ti,ab.
28 or/1-27
29 prompt*.ti,ab.
30 28 and 29
31 limit 30 to english
32 limit 31 to dt=20221201-20260428

13.2 Appendix 2. Decision tree

Decision tree -Scoping review prompting objective 2

Review Objective

1. To explore methods that have been employed for generating prompts in health care studies.
2. To identify studies with the explicit aim of describing the process of building prompts for large language models in healthcare.

Read the title and abstract.

13.3 Appendix 3. Draft data extraction form

This form may be updated after the pilot phase

Objective 1. Guidance on prompt generation	
Code	Options
Title	
Type of document	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Report ▪ Peer-reviewed article
Open access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Yes ▪ No
Link	Link or DOI
Journal name	
Publication year	Year of publication or last updated
First author	Example: Lopez-Alcalde J.
First author's region	
First author's country	
Institution/Company	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Claude ▪ OpenAI ▪ University ▪ Hospital ▪ ...
LLM name, version and date	
Health-related field in which prompts are intended to be applied	Example: Oncology
Task for which the prompt is used	
Target populations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Patients ▪ Documents ▪ ...
Guidance's purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Free text ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Definition of prompt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Free text ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Main focus of the guidance <i>Judged by reviewer</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ General principles of prompt generation ▪ Avoid errors in prompting ▪ Prompt architecture ▪ ... ▪ Unclear
Definition of prompt generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Free text ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Terminology used for prompt generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prompt generation ▪ Prompt building ▪ Prompt development ▪ Prompt engineering ▪ Prompt validation ▪ Prompt evaluation ▪ ...
Principles provided in the guidance <i>Select one or more</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Clarity and specificity ▪ Instructional details ▪ Structure and formatting ▪ Iteration and refinement ▪ Knowledge and creativity

	▪...
Phases of prompt generation considered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Phase 1: Building or development ▪ Phase 2: Validation or evaluation ▪ Other ▪ Unclear
Recommendations on datasets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Size ▪ Characteristics ▪....
Techniques explained in the guidance <i>Select one or more</i>	<p>Basic level techniques: Direct instruction Open-Ended prompting Zero-shot prompting Keyword-Based prompting Time-conditioned prompting Step by step instruction prompting Confirmatory prompting Template-based prompting Negative prompting Iterative prompting Contextual prompting Constraint-based prompting</p> <p>Advanced level techniques: Chain-of-Thought Prompting Role-Based Prompting Persona-Based Prompting Interactive Dialogue Prompting Multi-turn Prompting Reinforcement Prompting Comparison Prompting Scenario-Based Prompting Conditional Prompting Interactive Role Adaptation Bias Mitigation Prompting Cultural Context Prompting Task Decomposition Prompting Recursive Prompting Anchoring Prompting Context Expansion Prompting</p> <p>Other None of the above</p>
Elements proposed for the prompt architecture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Role ▪ Context ▪
Prompt techniques <i>As reported by the authors</i>	
Type of metrics for prompt building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Qualitative ▪ Quantitative ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Metrics for prompt building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sensitivity ▪ Specificity ▪

Type of metrics for prompt validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Qualitative ▪ Quantitative ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Metrics for prompt validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sensitivity ▪ Specificity ▪
Guidance on the databases for prompts generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Present for prompt building ▪ Present for prompt validation ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Relevant warnings about prompt generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Detail
Gaps in knowledge	

Objective 2. Methods used for prompt generation in health studies	
Code	Options
Title	
Open access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Yes ▪ No
Link	Link or DOI
Journal name	
Publication year	Year of publication or last updated
First author	Example: Lopez-Alcalde J.
First author's region	
First author's country	
Institution/Company	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Claude ▪ OpenAI ▪ University ▪ Hospital ▪ ...
LLM name, version and date	
Study dates <i>When the study was done</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Detail ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Health-related field in which prompts are intended to be applied	Example: Oncology
Task for which the prompt is used	
Target populations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Patients ▪ Documents ▪ ...
Study aim <i>As reported by the authors</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Free text ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Study design <i>As reported by the authors</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Detail ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Methods <i>Brief description</i>	
Sample size estimation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Done ▪ Not estimated ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Observed sample size	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ... ▪ Not estimated ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Definition of prompt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Free text ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Definition of prompt generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Free text ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Terminology used for prompt generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Prompt generation ▪ Prompt building ▪ Prompt development ▪ Prompt engineering ▪ Prompt validation ▪ Prompt evaluation ▪ ...

Phases of prompt generation considered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Phase 1: Building or development ▪ Phase 2: Validation or evaluation ▪ Other ▪ Unclear
Techniques explained in the guidance <i>Select one or more</i>	<p>Basic level techniques: Direct instruction Open-Ended prompting Zero-shot prompting Keyword-Based prompting Time-conditioned prompting Step by step instruction prompting Confirmatory prompting Template-based prompting Negative prompting Iterative prompting Contextual prompting Constraint-based prompting</p> <p>Advanced level techniques: Chain-of-Thought Prompting Role-Based Prompting Persona-Based Prompting Interactive Dialogue Prompting Multi-turn Prompting Reinforcement Prompting Comparison Prompting Scenario-Based Prompting Conditional Prompting Interactive Role Adaptation Bias Mitigation Prompting Cultural Context Prompting Task Decomposition Prompting Recursive Prompting Anchoring Prompting Context Expansion Prompting</p> <p>Other None of the above</p>
Prompt used	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reported ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Prompt techniques <i>As reported by the authors</i>	
Elements proposed for the prompt architecture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Role ▪ Context ▪
Type of metrics for prompt building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Qualitative ▪ Quantitative ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Metrics for prompt building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sensitivity ▪ Specificity ▪
Metrics for prompt validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sensitivity

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Specificity ▪
Guidance on the databases for prompts generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Present for prompt building ▪ Present for prompt validation ▪ Reported but unclear ▪ Not reported
Main findings about prompt use and performance	
Gaps in knowledge detected	